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NEST InGrained ecosystem for zEro EmissioN buildings

D1.4 STAKEHOLDERS ENGAGEMENT PLAN

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Terms, definitions and abbreviated terms

DC	Demonstration Case
EU	European Union
GA	Grant Agreement
HOAI	Honorarordnung für Architekten und Ingenieurs
SME	Small Medium (size) Enterprise
SP	Standardised Package
WP	Work Package
ZeB	Zero emissions Building

1. Executive summary

GREENEST project aims to create an ecosystem that integrates CO₂ neutral building materials with renewable energy sources into the building design, together with human response and natural systems, in order to demonstrate resource efficient construction that needs less materials and implements energy-efficient construction practices. For this reason, GREENEST will deliver a palette of innovative and sustainable solutions for new buildings which will address all stages of a building's lifetime. These solutions will be demonstrated in four new construction projects in three different countries (Germany, Italy and Greece), by using the local and regional supply chains.

This deliverable is part of WP1 activities, which are focusing on establishing the framework for the creation of the ecosystem and recognising the potential value chains, in each country, as well as the requirements of the sites where the new construction projects will be build. More specifically, in order to specify the characteristics of each ecosystem that will be demonstrated in each different country, the site requirements of the demonstration buildings should be defined, as well as the needs and the expectations of the owners of the demonstration sites. The possibility to use local and natural materials at the demo site areas, is also investigated in this deliverable by the recognition of the local suppliers and stakeholders.

All these data, will assist in the identification of the technologies and the GREENEST solutions that should be applied in each demo site and will also, define all the interested parties that should be considered, informed and involved in each demo site. In this way, the basic information needed for the preliminary design of the new buildings is collected.

In this deliverable, the demonstration site requirements are defined and the needs of the related stakeholders are identified. Moreover, the interested parties and local stakeholders are mapped and categorised, in order to create a plan including the strategies proposed for their engagement throughout the project. This plan will be ideally updated during the project, with new information and additional stakeholders. This deliverable will be also used as a guide for the following tasks of WP1.

2. Planned Criteria (Extract from DoA)

According to the Grant Agreement of the GreeNest project, a social task force will be created for each demo building to analyse site requirements and specify the development drivers for the different SPs from a user perspective. A stakeholder-centred approach will define the drivers for adopting the different technologies to help technology providers to improve their final products. A Stakeholder Engagement Plan will be designed providing detailed instructions on how to engage local and national networks of stakeholders accessible to the partners from the beginning of the project. First, focus groups meetings, workshops (online or in person) with stakeholders will be proposed. Surveys will be designed to determine and understand final users' needs. The outcome of this task will be the production of a Stakeholders Engagement Plan which will guide the activities in WP3 and WP6.

3. Introduction

3.1 Purpose and scope of the document

The purpose of this document is to first identify the needs and requirements of each demonstration site, in order to be then analysed in the next tasks and deliverables of the project, so as to contribute to the optimisation and improvement of the GreenNest technologies, from the users' perspective.

The users' perspective will be approached with the aid of surveys and questionnaires that will be distributed to them, or through workshops and meetings with them, so as to let them state their needs and their expectations from the project. At the same time, through these surveys, as well as through other social activities that will be developed in other Tasks of WP1, the users' awareness on energy efficiency and circularity will be increased.

Additionally, the stakeholders related to each demo site will be defined, in order to be contacted and engaged to the project. The level of influence, as well as the level of interest of each group of stakeholders will be categorised, to address them the appropriate amount of information. The main suppliers and contractors of the project will be identified and contacted to establish the local/regional supply chains channels.

This document includes all the aforementioned data and concludes with the plan for the Stakeholders engagement, which will guide the activities of other Tasks (see next paragraphs).

3.2 Relation to other activities and deliverables in the Project

Task 1.4 is directly related to Task 1.5 "Social activities tailored to the local contexts to ensure acceptance – design of "Living-Lab" "and Task 1.6 "Stakeholders engagement – Living Lab assessment", where the stakeholders engagement plan will be used to develop appropriate methodologies for the involvement of end-users to the project and the acceptance of the proposed technologies – ecosystems and of the new building materials from the citizens, professionals etc.

In addition, the definition of the site requirements will contribute to the preliminary design of the demonstration buildings and the needed SPs that should be integrated in each demo building.

Task 1.4 is also related to Task 4.1 "Establishment of sustainable value chains", where based on the stakeholders channels established in Task 1.4, a market value chain report will be produced.

Finally, the activities of this Task will provide input for WP6 (Task 6.3), in order to set up suitable business cases and business models for each of the three local value chains, covering three different EU markets and areas.

3.3 Contributing Partners

This Task is led by AMS with the contribution of other partners of the project and the assistance of the demo site leaders and owners. FENIX, HoWoGe, PILI, BGTec, KMAEL, MPV and LIG participate in this task, with TUB to be the demo site responsible for DC#1 (Museum “Pavilion and Knowledge Paths”), HoWoGe the responsible for DC#2 (Berlin lodge), MPV the responsible for DC#3 (Delta info-center) and AMS with MoS the responsible for DC#4 (North Aegean youth recreational centre). In the following table the contributions of the partners are indicated:

TABLE 1: PARTNER CONTRIBUTIONS

Partner	Contribution
AMS	Leader of Task, Preparation of D1.4, responsible for DC#4
FENIX	Participation in the meetings and review of the stakeholders’ map templates
HoWoGe	Contribution for DC#2 and related feedback for this demo, as DC#2 responsible
PILI	Light clay module information and feedback
BGTec	Contribution related to DC#3 – Porto Viro demo site
KMAEL	Contribution related to DC#1 demo site
MPV	Contribution for DC#3 and related feedback for this demo, as DC#3 responsible
LIGNUM	Participation in the meetings and review of the stakeholders’ map templates
TUB	Contribution for DC#1 and related feedback for this demo, as DC#1 responsible

4. Demonstration Site Requirements

4.1 DC#1 – Brief description of DC1 (Berlin Museum)

Demo Building #1 is a new Museum-Pavilion in the Campus of TU-Berlin. As a living lab for planning and building within planetary boundaries, it defines a future-oriented concept for the conception and construction of a sophisticated supporting structure made of reclaimed wood, a foundation made of recycled materials and a low-tech approach. The building site is located in the center of the University’s’ Campus City West (UCCW), just south of the main building. The proposed design emphasizes ecological ZeB construction, as well as to the surrounding environment with emphasis to the preservation of existing trees. The new building will be used as a museum – exhibition center – and knowledge hub. The eco-friendly design solutions of the building as a contribution to reach ZeB status, will be visible for visitors and part of future exhibitions, conferences, seminars, knowledge days for professionals, students and visitors.

General information:

Pilot Leader & design Partner: Eike Roswag-Klinge, Sina Jansen

Location: The demo building DC#1 is located in the center of Berlin, on the campus of TU Berlin.

FIGURE 1: DC#1– BERLIN MUSEUM LOCATION

Climate: oceanic climate bordering on a humid continental climate – summers are warm and sometimes humid. Winters are cold, though not very severe. Moderate rainfall throughout the year (see also DC#2).

Description of the existing state of the demo building area:

The design of the project has not been finalized; the project is currently completing planning phase 3 (according to the HOAI former Scale of Fees in Germany). According to the current timetable, the building application will be submitted to the examining authorities in 2024, the completion is planned for 2027.

The overall approach is the development of a reversible, circular building design which is optimized for the reuse of materials and building components. Following the GreenNest “DesignByInventory” approach, design decisions are oriented based on the existing material stockpile in Berlin and surrounding areas. The building will be built from renewable or reused materials, with the smallest possible footprint – in terms of carbon, resources but also sealing of soil.

The construction of the building is planned as follows:

- Flying Foundations: elevated building with point foundations optimized for the use of recycled material, with minimal use of cement and steel and sealing of soil
- Load-bearing structure: (waste-wood) timber frame with lattice grid & solid wood columns
- Ceilings/Slabs: solid WDLT-Slab and Earth Screed/DLT-Slab and wooden flooring/linoleum
- External walls: timber paneled construction
- Facade: textile facade with supporting steel structure, timber batting
- Internal walls: solid timber frame walls
- Openings: wood-aluminum triple sun-protection glazed windows, timber doors
- Roof: solid timber slab (flat roof), intensive green roof on substrate, water retention box
- Roof & wall insulation: KARZ/wood fiber insulation

4.1.1 Site requirements

By Law / Regulations Requirements (similar to DC#2)

According to the existing applicable regulations in Berlin (BauO Bln), the Architectural Design is part of the prerequisites to obtain the Building Permit and should at least include the following:

- a) Extract from cadastral map and the site plan
- b) Floor plans, sections, elevations of the area under construction
- c) Building and operating description
- d) Proof of stability
- e) Proof of fire protection
- f) Proof of energy savings

- g) Information on the secured development with regard to the supply of water and energy as well as the disposal of wastewater and the traffic-related development

The surrounding area – the central part of the TU Berlin campus - is a listed garden monument. Therefore, the design of demo building DC#1 must meet the requirements of the heritage protection.

4.1.2 End-user & owners' requirements

The museum pavilion houses TU Berlin's permanent mineralogical exhibition, a temporary exhibition area and knowledge hub with an experimental laboratory, a museum café, offices and an information desk on a total area of approx. — 1,250 m². The pavilion serves as the new centre of the campus with newly implemented knowledge trails, guiding tourists across the South Campus. The building intends to make the implemented principles of sustainable construction visible and tangible to visitors and users. This is reflected particularly in the future-oriented wooden construction and the innovative low-tech concept. The needs and requirements by users and owner have been identified in a number of qualitative formats and methods, as well as written summaries that have been continuously updated throughout the process.

- With exceptional high conservatory demands and comfort standards, museums usually play a big role in the energy and resource consumption worldwide. In contrast to that, the planned exhibits of the mineralogical exhibition and uses of the demo building DC#1 do not meet these requirements and qualify the project for a sustainable-oriented climate and building design based on the principles of efficiency, consistency, resilience and sufficiency. As a living lab for the planning and building within planetary boundaries the project aims to define new technique-reduced, sustainable approaches for public buildings (and museums) in Berlin, Germany and beyond.
- A yearly number of 20.000-25.000 visitors is expected and condition of the projects funding. Therefore, a number of innovative and interactive formats are currently developed to attract different kind of visitors, from researchers & scientists, to students and teachers, universities staff, as well as civil society and citizens.
- Instead of an architectural competition, the conceptual preliminary design planning was developed under the expert guidance of Prof. Eike Roswag-Klinge and Sina Jansen, Natural Building Lab at TU Berlin, as part of a teaching research project by master's students at the TU Berlin in the fields of architecture, landscape architecture and civil engineering. This collaborative process was accompanied by an external advisory board consisting of experts from the fields of architecture, design, landscape architecture, exhibition, heritage preservation and tourism planning. The design proposal from the interdisciplinary student office was handed over to the planning team during a joint workshop and is now being further developed in the preliminary design planning - as far as the legal and local framework conditions allow. Architects, engineers and artists are involved as required.

4.2 DC#2 – Brief description of DC2 (Berlin lodge)

4.2.1 Site requirements

DC#2 is a new student housing project. HOWOGE aims to make a high-quality and sustainable contribution to the creation of urgently needed affordable housing in Berlin. The EcoTechWall panels will be part of the façade of the HOWOGE’s residential building.

General information:

Pilot leader: Geraldine Abbate

Location: DC#2 is located in Berlin (Germany) in the district of Lichtenberg. The demonstration building is right next to the “Tierpark” Berlin, the larger of Berlin’s two zoological gardens and situated close to the University of Economics.

FIGURE 2: DC#2 – BERLIN LODGE LOCATION

Climate: Oceanic climate bordering on a humid continental climate – summers are warm and sometimes humid. Winters are cold, though not very severe. Moderate rainfall throughout the year. Below, in Figure 3, the yearly average temperature values are illustrated

Climate data for Berlin (Brandenburg), 1991–2020, extremes 1957–2021													[hide]
Month	Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May	Jun	Jul	Aug	Sep	Oct	Nov	Dec	Year
Record high °C (°F)	15.1 (59.2)	19.2 (66.6)	25.8 (78.4)	30.8 (87.4)	32.7 (90.9)	38.4 (101.1)	38.3 (100.9)	38.0 (100.4)	32.3 (90.1)	27.7 (81.9)	20.9 (69.6)	15.6 (60.1)	38.4 (101.1)
Mean maximum °C (°F)	10.6 (51.1)	12.4 (54.3)	17.9 (64.2)	24.0 (75.2)	28.4 (83.1)	31.5 (88.7)	32.7 (90.9)	32.7 (90.9)	26.9 (80.4)	21.5 (70.7)	14.8 (58.6)	11.2 (52.2)	34.8 (94.6)
Mean daily maximum °C (°F)	3.2 (37.8)	4.9 (40.8)	9.0 (48.2)	15.1 (59.2)	19.6 (67.3)	22.9 (73.2)	25.0 (77.0)	24.8 (76.6)	19.8 (67.6)	13.9 (57.0)	7.7 (45.9)	4.1 (39.4)	14.2 (57.5)
Daily mean °C (°F)	0.7 (33.3)	1.6 (34.9)	4.6 (40.3)	9.7 (49.5)	14.2 (57.6)	17.6 (63.7)	19.6 (67.3)	19.2 (66.6)	14.7 (58.5)	9.6 (49.3)	4.9 (40.8)	1.8 (35.2)	9.9 (49.8)
Mean daily minimum °C (°F)	-2.2 (28.0)	-1.8 (28.8)	0.4 (32.7)	4.0 (39.2)	8.2 (46.8)	11.7 (53.1)	14.0 (57.2)	13.5 (56.3)	9.8 (49.6)	5.6 (42.1)	1.9 (35.4)	-0.9 (30.4)	5.3 (41.6)
Mean minimum °C (°F)	-12.0 (10.4)	-9.5 (14.9)	-5.8 (21.6)	-2.6 (27.3)	1.7 (35.1)	6.3 (43.3)	8.9 (48.0)	8.1 (46.6)	3.9 (39.0)	-1.3 (29.7)	-5.0 (23.0)	-8.9 (16.0)	-14.2 (6.4)
Record low °C (°F)	-25.3 (-13.5)	-22.0 (-7.6)	-19.1 (-2.4)	-7.4 (18.7)	-2.8 (27.0)	1.3 (34.3)	4.9 (40.8)	4.6 (40.3)	-0.9 (30.4)	-7.7 (18.1)	-17.8 (0.0)	-24.0 (-11.2)	-25.3 (-13.5)
Average precipitation mm (inches)	41.5 (1.63)	30.0 (1.18)	35.9 (1.41)	27.7 (1.09)	52.8 (2.08)	60.2 (2.37)	70.0 (2.76)	52.4 (2.06)	43.6 (1.72)	40.3 (1.59)	38.8 (1.53)	39.1 (1.54)	532.3 (20.96)
Average precipitation days (≥ 0.1 mm)	15.8	13.9	14	10.9	12.8	12.4	13.4	12.7	11.6	13.6	14.5	16.4	162
Average snowy days (≥ 1.0 cm)	8.4	6.8	2.6	0.2	0	0	0	0	0	0	1.4	4.9	24.3
Average relative humidity (%)	85.9	81.2	75.8	67.2	66.9	66.3	67	68.5	76	82.7	87.8	87.5	76.1
Mean monthly sunshine hours	52.6	77.9	126.7	196.4	231.1	232.9	233.7	222.2	168.9	113.8	57.4	45.0	1,758.6

Source 1: Data derived from Deutscher Wetterdienst^[89]
Source 2: NCEI(days with precipitation and snow, humidity)^[90]

FIGURE 3: WEATHER DATA FOR BERLIN GERMANY (<https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Berlin>)

Description of the existing state of the demo building area:

The planning of the building has not yet been finalised. The plan is to construct small apartments for students in a timber hybrid design (modular or elemental timber system construction).

By Law / Regulations Requirements

According to the existing applicable regulations in Berlin (BauO Bln), the Architectural Design is part of the prerequisites to obtain the Building Permit and should at least include the following:

- a) Extract from cadastral map and the site plan
- b) Floor plans, sections, elevations of the area under construction
- c) Building and operating description
- d) Proof of stability
- e) Proof of fire protection
- f) Proof of energy savings

Information on the secured development with regard to the supply of water and energy, as well as the disposal of wastewater and the traffic-related development.

4.2.2 End-user & owners' requirements

- The building operates as a student residence. In view of the continuing high demand for housing in the city and the steady population growth in Berlin, thousands of new flats will be needed in the coming years. Affordable living space is particularly in demand, both in terms of basic rent and ancillary costs. This requires an efficient use of space and at the same time a high quality of the building to be constructed in terms of living comfort and durability. This also includes consideration of climatic conditions and careful use of resources.
- It has to be taken into serious consideration that many people are not familiarized with smart control or computerized systems; therefore, it is a necessity to keep the controls as simple as possible.

4.3 DC#3 – Brief description of DC3 (Porto Viro – Delta Info Centre)

4.3.1 Site requirements

DC#3 is located in Porto Levante (a suburb of Porto Viro Municipality). The building site is located within the since 1999 UNESCO’s World Heritage area of Porto Levante and the new building will serve the local port as an info-center for the tourists and as a recovery /maintenance depo for the lagoon’s boats of recreational use.

General information:

Pilot leader: Arch. Davide Marangoni

Pilot design partner: Arch. Davide Marangoni

Location: The Italian demo is located in river Po Delta area in particular in PORTO VIRO municipality belonging to the Province of Rovigo at the Italian region Veneto, located about 45 km south of Venice and about 35 km east of Rovigo. The site is located in Porto Levante to the right of the mouth of Po di Levante. It presents itself as a typical fishing settlement, recently converted to seaside and nature tourism, in fact there’s also a dock for pleasure boating. The space in which the building will be located is in a strategic position between Po di Levante and the tourist port.

FIGURE 4: ITALIAN DEMO SITE AREA PHOTOS

Climate: The Italian demo is located in the Municipality of Porto Viro, in a cool - summer Mediterranean climate area.

FIGURE 5: LOCALIZATION OF PORTO LEVANTE SITE

The building area will be characterized from reinforced concrete with recycled steel; facade area: 121.2m² by timber studs and walls; Load-bearing and bracing interior walls by solid wood construction; Non-load bearing interior walls by lightweight construction; roof area approx. 60m², similar to floor slabs with ceramic tiles; timber framed triple glazed windows 3.5 m²; E/M installations (plumbing, electrics, ventilation system); surrounding area and landscaping.

4.3.2 End-user & owners' requirements

The building operates as tourist info point but also, as a warehouse for fishermen. The high number of tourists in particular during the spring-summer period in the Delta Po area will permit to this Demo Building to guarantee a valid physical site, where tourists can receive information useful to visit Delta po area with bicycles, or by walk, or by boat tours. Porto Levante represents an excellent starting point for excursions on the river, into the large surrounding lagoons, or to the Adriatic Sea. Through this navigable canal it is possible to reach the cities of Rovigo, Mantova, Ferrara, Cremona and Piacenza. Starting from the mouth of the Po di Levante, it is possible to experience a fascinating and exhaustive navigation route, entering the numerous canals that allow you to reach other in land river ports. The village of Porto Levante, overlooking the lagoon area of Sacca Cavallari, separated from the sea by the homonymous sandbar (or "scanno"), looks like a typical fishing village, with low and colourful houses, a characteristic 18th century church and a rich wooded area, which preserves an old icehouse and is a great place for locals to come for pleasant walks.

In other periods of the year, the same Demo Building will serve as warehouse for fishermen. Indeed, Porto Levante area is devoted to the activities related to fishing and aquaculture; due to their historical and

traditional value, play an important role in the economic and employment area and are always well received within the Delta Po Park.

Due to the great number of visitors or fishermen that the site could gather, specific care should be taken for the safety of people from fire or other hazards (comply with fire regulations, create the necessary emergency exits, have a fire safety plan ready and mounted in an exposed area, etc.).

4.4 DC#4 – Brief description of DC4 (North Aegean Recreational Centre)

DC#4 is located on Lesvos Island (Mytilene) in the North coast of the island and more specifically in the village named “Stypsi”. The demonstration building is situated close to the old oil refinery and the aim of the Stypsi Municipality is to create a youth recreational center where activities of education, exercise, teaching and relaxation could take place.

The inhabitants of Stypsi village mainly make their living by livestock farming, cultivation of olive trees and stone carving. There is a tradition in building their houses from wood and stone and thus, many specialized technicians in the area have expertise in using these materials.

General information:

Pilot construction leader: Constantinos Tsoutis, Construction Engineer

Pilot design partner: Maria Sachini, Architect

Location: The Greek demo site is located in the Municipality of Stypsi, in the island of Lesvos, North – East Aegean, approximately 260km south from the city of Athens.

FIGURE 6: DC#4 – NORTH AEGEAN DEMO SITE LOCATION

Climate: Mediterranean – Relatively mild and short winter with a lot of rain. Summer is hot with only a few rainfalls. Strong north & north-west winds. Below, the yearly average temperature values are illustrated:

Climate data for Mytilene (1955-2010 averages)													[hide]
Month	Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May	Jun	Jul	Aug	Sep	Oct	Nov	Dec	Year
Record high °C (°F)	20.2 (68.4)	21.3 (70.3)	28.0 (82.4)	31.0 (87.8)	35.0 (95.0)	40.0 (104.0)	39.5 (103.1)	38.2 (100.8)	36.2 (97.2)	30.8 (87.4)	27.0 (80.6)	22.5 (72.5)	40.0 (104.0)
Mean daily maximum °C (°F)	12.2 (54.0)	12.8 (55.0)	15 (59)	19.3 (66.7)	24.3 (75.7)	28.9 (84.0)	31 (88)	30.8 (87.4)	27 (81)	22 (72)	17.4 (63.3)	13.9 (57.0)	20.9 (69.6)
Daily mean °C (°F)	9.5 (49.1)	9.9 (49.8)	11.6 (52.9)	15.6 (60.1)	20.2 (68.4)	24.7 (76.5)	26.6 (79.9)	26.1 (79.0)	22.9 (73.2)	18.5 (65.3)	14.3 (57.7)	11.3 (52.3)	17.6 (63.7)
Mean daily minimum °C (°F)	6.8 (44.2)	7.0 (44.6)	8.2 (46.8)	11.4 (52.5)	15.3 (59.5)	19.6 (67.3)	22 (72)	21.7 (71.1)	18.6 (65.5)	15 (59)	11.4 (52.5)	8.7 (47.7)	13.7 (56.7)
Record low °C (°F)	-4.4 (24.1)	-3 (27)	-1.2 (29.8)	4.0 (39.2)	8.4 (47.1)	11.0 (51.8)	15.8 (60.4)	16.3 (61.3)	10.9 (51.6)	5.2 (41.4)	1.4 (34.5)	-1.4 (29.5)	-4.4 (24.1)
Average precipitation mm (inches)	111 (4.4)	96.2 (3.79)	70.1 (2.76)	44.8 (1.76)	19.8 (0.78)	6.4 (0.25)	2 (0.1)	2.7 (0.11)	12.4 (0.49)	43.9 (1.73)	97.1 (3.82)	138.7 (5.46)	670.6 (26.40)
Average precipitation days (≥ 1.0 mm)	9.0	8.1	6.5	4.8	2.7	0.8	0.4	0.4	1.3	3.3	6.8	10.0	54.1
Average relative humidity (%)	71.0	69.8	57.5	63.9	62.6	57.3	56.0	57.4	59.5	66.1	71.0	72.0	64.5
Source 1: Hellenic National Meteorological Service ^[45]													
Source 2: NOAA ^[46]													

FIGURE 7: WEATHER DATA FOR LESBOS GREECE (<https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Lesbos>)

Description of the existing state of the demo building area:

The demonstration building will be constructed from scratch in the area of the old oil refinery premises and will be used as a museum and recreation area. The existing structures of the area are old and ruined buildings which will be refurbished, and a new building will be built in the framework of the GreeNest project to be used as cultural and recreational centre.

The basic materials of the already existing buildings and structures of the area are timber, stone and bricks, whereas all buildings of the village have a pitched roof consisted of ceramic tiles in the color of terracotta (this is mainly imposed by the traditional settlement’s regulations).

FIGURE 8: DEMONSTRATION SITE TOP VIEW (AREA IN YELLOW CIRCLE INDICATES THE NEW BUILDING)

The main construction data of the building that will be built on the north side of the described area is:

- Foundations: Reinforced concrete/recycled steel
- Floors: Timber oak flooring
- External walls: Natural stone & Mortar, Concrete Beams
- External finishing: Natural Stone finishing
- Internal walls: Masonry (Brick)
- Openings: Timber framed double glazed windows and timber doors
- Roof: Single pitch, timber framed roof with ceramic tiles (terracotta)
- Wall's insulation: SmartWall's insulation material – sheep wool
- Roof insulation: SmartRoof's insulation material – sheep wool

4.4.1 Site requirements

By Law / Regulations Requirements:

According to the existing applicable regulations in Greece (NOK 2012, KENAK 2017, Fire Safety Regulation, etc.), the Architectural Design is part of the prerequisites to obtain the Building Permit and for non-tendered by Public Procurement Projects, should at least include the following:

- a) Site Plan;
- b) Floor plans, sections, elevations of the area under construction / renovation for both existing and renovated state;
- c) Lighting & fresh air supply plans or calculations update;
- d) Fire Escape Routes Plan update;
- e) Building's Energy Efficiency Calculations;
- f) Health & Safety Plan;
- g) Declarations of Conformity by the designer;
- h) Minimum Construction Cost (Official document for owner's Social Security Contributions).

All the aforementioned laws and regulations, impose specific rules in the way that the new buildings are constructed, the way of preparing the related plans, drawings and documents and the way to succeed the energy performance targets.

Law 4315/24.12.201434 imposes that every new building which is located in settlements < 2000 population, should comply with the Settlement's Architectural Type which imposes limitations and restrictions on both design and materials that can be used in order to match the aesthetics of the settlement.

Stypsi Municipality's additional basic technical requirements – instructions:

Additionally to the above mentioned fundamental instructions, the Municipality of Stypsi expressed the following basic requirements:

- External walls must be made of stone or have natural stone finishing;
- Internal wall finishing must be white coloured or have earth tone colour hues;
- Doors and windows must have earth tone colour hues;
- The roof must have roofing tiles matching the aesthetics of the area;
- Ideally use of eco-friendly and local materials (stone, timber, etc).

Demo Site's nature, geometry and shape:

The results of the detailed site survey executed, indicated a range of limitations / constrains / considerations, occurring by the site's nature, topography and shape, as following:

- The demo site area is on the top of a hill and there is no highway or other large road which can drive to the site, therefore the trucks and cranes that ideally will be needed to be used during the works cannot easily reach the site (this should be considered for the transportation and handling of materials).
- Special care should be exercised for the preservation of the existing trees inside the site area (if possible).
- Alternative ways / roads should be identified to make possible the delivery of materials and bulky components to the site.

4.4.2 End-user & owners' requirements

- The Greek Demo Site building will operate as a youth recreational center. It will be an extension to the old oil refinery of the village of Stypsi, which will also comprise local product corner shops, administration offices, a museum and a garden, alongside their auxiliary spaces. These attributes add to the publicity and hospitality of the premises.
- The environment of the Greek demo site is traditional (rural) and will be welcoming mostly visits of agricultural, educational and touristic interest. This means that the target groups and main users of the Greek demo site are young visitors (students), local producers and residents, office workers, tourists and individuals interested in the general tradition, agriculture and landscape of the village, for leisure and education. That is why the eco-friendly and green character of the demonstration building should be emphasised.

- It has to be taken into serious consideration that many people are not familiar with smart control or computerized systems; therefore, it is a necessity to keep the controls and automations of the building as simple as possible.
- Additionally, for safety reasons, new technologies should be well assimilated into the character of the surrounding environment and be maintained exclusively by specialized individuals.
- Due to the great number of visitors that the site could gather, specific care should be taken for the safety of people from fire hazards (comply with fire regulations, create the necessary emergency exits, have a fire safety plan ready and mounted in an exposed area, etc.).

4.5 End-users’ needs and requirements defined

As a conclusion from the previous chapters concerning the site and stakeholders’ requirements for each demonstration case, the following needs and/or requirements were defined in terms of users’ perspective:

TABLE 2: DEMO SITES USERS’ NEEDS

Demonstration Site	Region	Users & Related Needs
Museum “Pavilion & Knowledge Paths”	Berlin – Germany	Visitors, academics, tourists: High comfort standards, sustainable construction, low energy and resource consumption, efficiency of systems.
Berlin Lodge	Berlin – Germany	Students: Affordable living in terms of costs, comfort, efficient use of space, user-friendly controls and heating/cooling systems.
Delta Info-centre	Porto Viro – Italy	Tourists/fishermen: Safe construction, storage areas for serving as warehouse, fire and earthquake safety plan.
North Aegean youth recreational centre	Lesvos – Greece	Tourists, students, professionals: Nice landscaping for walk and exercise, easy to use systems (E/M), fire safety, easy maintenance and repair of systems.

5. Stakeholders Mapping

5.1 Definition of Stakeholders

In order to be able to meet the requirements described in the previous paragraphs, the needs and the expectations of all the parties interested in the project should be discovered and then aligned with the communicated and non-communicated derived requirements.

The term “stakeholder” is used as a general term to describe individuals, groups, or organizations that have an interest in a project and can mobilize resources to affect its outcome in some way. They are usually entities that may be affected or have an effect or effort in the project. They could also develop or conduct the project.

Therefore, the successful completion of a project is mainly depending on its relevant stakeholders and their interests. In order to spot the interested people of a project, a mapping procedure is usually followed. Then, these stakeholders should be contacted so as to find out their needs and expectations.

Stakeholders mapping refers to the process of identifying the relevant stakeholders in a project and assists in their engagement throughout the project. The aim of stakeholders’ map is to recognise the “key players” who can interfere and affect the progress and success of the project. The stakeholder map will then serve as a guide for the completion of the Stakeholders Engagement Plan.

5.2 Benefits of stakeholder mapping

Through stakeholder mapping and analysis, the stakeholders are defined, and their interests and influence are approached. At the same time, it is easier to identify how the project can affect them and be able to categorize them.

Mapping of stakeholders produces a visualisation of the participants of a project and gives a clear idea of their relationship with the project and between them. In that way, their positive engagement can be reinforced, and any delays or conflicts may be avoided.

1. Stakeholders mapping helps in clarifying who the relevant stakeholders are and create a prioritisation list according to their relation to the project;
2. Can assist in the categorisation of the interested parties in a project;
3. Understand the background and the way of thinking of each stakeholders group or team, so that they can be appropriately engaged and contacted;
4. Mapping can help to recognise the key stakeholders and therefore focus on them from the beginning of the project;
5. Develop communication strategies according to the nature and background of each stakeholders group;
6. Helps establishing realistic time plans based on the available time and resources.

7. Can finally assist in identifying the relationships between different stakeholders and therefore create teams or potential collaborations between them, so as to promote the progress of the project.

5.3 Tools for Stakeholders Mapping

There are many tools that can be used for the stakeholders mapping, some of those are more traditional tools and some others are more modern approaches. Depending on the complexity of the project, different simple tools can be used or combinations of them, taking also into account their user-friendliness and the familiarization of the users with them.

Large projects may have hundreds of stakeholders; therefore, it is crucial to be able to classify them according to their importance and prominence.

1. The **salience method** is used to classify the stakeholders according to their power, legitimacy and urgency, into seven categories (dormant, discretionary, demanding, dominant, dangerous, dependent, and definitive). This method helps in quickly identifying who are the most important stakeholders and proposes engaging different stakeholder types in specific ways. The following diagrams are used in this method.

FIGURE 9: SALIENCE METHOD DIAGRAMS

2. Other common tool is the **stakeholder's relationship network** which depicts the relationships between stakeholders and how these can affect the project. Also, this method can identify the connections that each stakeholder has even outside the project and expand the project's network by building relationships with these new connections. Below are presented the diagrams used for the stakeholder's relationship network:

FIGURE 10: RELATIONSHIP NETWORK DIAGRAMS

3. **Stakeholder mapping spreadsheets** are very easy to use and offer a flexible way to map all the participants of a project by adding as many columns as needed in order to include all the needed attributes.

Stakeholder Type	Contact	Topics of Interest	Impact level
Owner	name@emailaddress.com	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Costs and margins • Risks • Legislation 	High
Project manager	name@emailaddress.com	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Timelines • New hires • New capabilities 	High
Team member	name@emailaddress.com	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Personal development opportunities • Promotions 	Medium
Local business	name@emailaddress.com	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Business opportunities • Local population changes 	Medium
Resident	name@emailaddress.com	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Traffic impacts • Environmental impacts • Noise 	High

FIGURE 11: SIMPLE STAKEHOLDER’S MAPPING SPREADSHEET¹

¹ <https://simplystakeholders.com/>

They can be as simple as the spreadsheet depicted in Figure 11 or more complex as the one indicated below (Figure 12).

Stakeholders	Role in project	Level of Support	Interest	Impact/ Influence	Risks/ Uncertainties	Strategies	Interact Preferences
Sarah Thompson	Project Manager	xxx	●	●	Budget overruns may impact timelines. Mitigation essential for project success	Continuous monitoring, regular security audits, employee training, swift response to emerging threats	Email sarah@email.com Phone +1-555-123-4567
xxx	xxx	xxx	●	●	Xxxxxxxxxx xxxxx	Xxxxxx Xxxxxx xxxxxxxx	Xxxxxx Xxxxxx xxxxxxx
xxx	xxxx	xxx	●	●	Xxxxxx Xxxxxx xxxxxxx	Xxxxxx Xxxxxx xxxxxxx	Xxxxxx Xxxxxx xxxxxxx
xxx	xxx	xxx	●	●	Xxxxxx Xxxxxx xxxxxxx	Xxxxxx Xxxxxx xxxxxxx	Xxxxxx Xxxxxx xxxxxxx
xxx	xxx	xxx	●	●	Xxxxxx Xxxxxx xxxxxxx	Xxxxxx Xxxxxx xxxxxxx	Xxxxxx Xxxxxx xxxxxxx

FIGURE 12: STAKEHOLDER’S MAPPING SPREADSHEET USED IN GREENEST PROJECT²

However, this kind of tool has many limitations like the lack of visualisation, or the inability to depict the relationships between stakeholders. It is though a simple method and easy to be used by all the participants of the project.

4. **Power/Influence & Interest Grid or Matrix** is used to divide the stakeholders into four quadrants based on their level of interest and influence in the project. In each quadrant there is a different engagement proposed for each stakeholder depending on its interest or on its influence on the project. The different levels of engagement are the following:

² <https://templatelab.com/stakeholder-map/>

FIGURE 13: MATRIXES USED FOR THE INFLUENCE/INTEREST GRID

- High power / high interest – Proposed engagement activities→ Manage closely, regularly engage, and manage expectations.
- High power / low interest – Proposed engagement activities→Meet their needs, keep them satisfied, and actively consult.
- Low power / low interest – Proposed engagement activities→Monitor and provide information as needed.
- Low power / high interest – Proposed engagement activities→Keep informed and maintain interest.

Some of the models and tools described, are over-simplistic or lacking information that could be valuable. Others can be more complex as a tool and can be hard to use. Therefore, it is essential to choose the right tool that best fits each specific project and combine it, if necessary, with other tools in order to create the best possible outcomes and outputs.

5.4 Stakeholders’ groups involved (for each DC)

After identifying the stakeholders through the appropriate mapping tool, the next step is to classify or categorise them into groups. This can assist in understanding them and manage them properly and according to their needs. Also, the categorisation of the stakeholders will aid to the organizing of tailored social activities for each group of stakeholders focusing on the end-users and key stakeholders involvement (Task 1.5).

One way to characterise stakeholders is by their related interest and influence to the project. In that case they can be categorised as **primary, secondary and key stakeholders**. Key stakeholders are those that present a higher potential risk and their role is critical for the success of a project. Key stakeholders need to be prioritised and require a closer management and engagement.

Another type of classification and simpler one is to categorise them into **internal** and **external** stakeholders depending on their relationship to the project (whether inside or outside the project team). Internal are those that are typically directly involved in the project, like the project team, project managers etc. In contrast, external stakeholders may be the suppliers, clients, or government bodies.

Other classifications may be related to the needs, or expectations they have from the project, or from their background.

The stakeholders related to the activities of the GreeNest project are mainly the following:

- a) Owners and building administrators (internal, key stakeholder)
- b) Users/ Inhabitants (internal, primary stakeholders)
- c) Material suppliers (external, secondary stakeholders)
- d) Workers: Labourers who contribute to the construction process according to the guidelines of the manufacturers of the standardised packages (internal, secondary stakeholders)
- e) Local Community and neighbours: Residents and businesses adjacent to the demonstration buildings. These are maybe affected by noise, dust and traffic during the installation of the GreeNest technologies (external, secondary stakeholders)
- f) Public authorities and bodies (external, key stakeholders)
- g) Project team and managers (internal, key stakeholders)

5.4.1 DC#1 – Museum Pavilion & Knowledge Paths

In the demo building DC#1 internal and external stakeholders are related to the implementation of the GreeNest solutions. They can be characterised and categorised as internal and external as followed, differentiating between directly involved and passive stakeholders.

The stakeholder map of DC#1 will be further developed and reviewed as the project progresses. Depending on the state of the project different relevance levels of the different stakeholder groups are expected.

Internal stakeholders

1. Owner and building administrator: TU Berlin
2. Project team & managers: Natural Building Lab, TU Berlin
3. Extended project team: INEB, KMAEL, DAIK, THOLZ, HAMS, METSOL
4. Planning team: ZRS Architekten
5. Internal Users: TU Berlin (mineralogical collection, research and teaching institutions, students, etc.)

External stakeholders

1. External Users: café tenant, visitors, students, researchers & scientists

2. Public authorities and bodies: Bezirksamt Charlottenburg-Wilmersdorf, Berlin Senate (funding institution), monument protection authority
3. Material suppliers: General contractor, building firms, timber construction company, waste-wood supplier and processing company
4. Workers: carpenters, construction workers
5. Local Community: staff, students, professors

GREENEST PROJECT STAKEHOLDER MAP

DEMO SITE 1

Museum "Pavilion & Knowledge Paths"

Site Requirements:
 Technologies – SPs to be implemented: SP1, SP 2, SP 3, SP 7, SP 14, SP 15, SP 16
 Value chains-suppliers: TUB, ZRS, INEB, KMAEL, DAIK, THOLZ, HAMS, METSOL

Deadline: Friday, April 19, 2024

Stakeholders	Role in project	Level of Support	Interest	Impact/ Influence	Risks/ Uncertainties	Strategies	Interact Preferences
Executive Board of Technical University Berlin	Building owner	medium	●	●	Budget overruns may lead to possible strategic & political project against the DC#1	Cost monitoring, potential analysis, pro-active project communication	through project manager
Audrey Podann (TUB)	Representative end-user; building operator; project manager	high	●	●	Budget overruns, personnel issues, lack of expertise in building related fields	Regular exchange & information, cost monitoring, project & time management	through research coordinator (TUB)
Sabine Kinzel (TUB)	Head of construction DC#1	high	●	●	Budget overruns, changes in timeline, organizational issues, error in authorization process	Cost monitoring, project & time management	through research coordinator (TUB)
René Vonau (TUB)	Head of department VI – Buildings and Services Management, TU Berlin	low	●	●	Complication in the coordination of the technical intersection of building/campus, issues in building operation	Regular exchange & updates on planning	Through project manager; head of construction
District of Berlin Charlottenburg-Wilmersdorf	Local authority; project representative; funding recipient	medium	●	●	none	Regular exchange & updates on planning	Through project manager; head of construction

GREENEST PROJECT STAKEHOLDER MAP

DEMO SITE 1

Museum "Pavilion & Knowledge Paths"

Site Requirements:
 Technologies – SPs to be implemented: SP1, SP 2, SP 3, SP 7, SP 14, SP 15, SP 16
 Value chains-suppliers: TUB, ZRS, INEB, KMAEL, DAIK, THOLZ, HAMS, METSOL

Deadline: Friday, April 19, 2024

Stakeholders	Role in project	Level of Support	Interest	Impact/ Influence	Risks/ Uncertainties	Strategies	Interact Preferences
Department „Science and Society“ (TUB)	End-user	high	●	●	Organisation of the building operation, funding of future exhibitions unclear	Active involvement, regular exchange & updates on planning	through research coordinator (TUB)
Mineralogical Collections (TUB)	End-user	high	●	●	none	Active involvement, regular exchange & updates on planning	through research coordinator (TUB)
City planning office, Berlin Charlottenburg-Wilmersdorf	local authority; project approval	low	●	●	Rejection of planning for urban development reasons	Active involvement & exchange on planning decisions before the submission of the building application	Through owner, project manager, head of construction
Historical Monuments office, Berlin Charlottenburg-Wilmersdorf	local authority; project approval	low	●	●	Rejection of planning for reasons of monument preservation	Active involvement & exchange on planning decisions before the submission of the building application	Through owner, project manager, head of construction
Garden Monuments office, Berlin Charlottenburg-Wilmersdorf	Local authority; project approval	low	●	●	Rejection of planning for reasons of monument preservation	Active involvement & exchange on planning decisions before the submission of the building application	Through owner, project manager, head of construction

GREENEST PROJECT STAKEHOLDER MAP

DEMO SITE 1

Museum "Pavilion & Knowledge Paths"

Site Requirements:
 Technologies – SPs to be implemented: SP1, SP 2, SP 3, SP 7, SP 14, SP 15, SP 16
 Value chains-suppliers: TUB, ZRS, INEB, KMAEL, DAIK, THOLZ, HAMS, METSOL

Deadline: Friday, April 19, 2024

Stakeholders	Role in project	Level of Support	Interest	Impact/ influence	Risks/ Uncertainties	Strategies	Interact Preferences
Nature-conservation authority, Berlin Charlottenburg-Wilmersdorf	local authority; project approval	low	●	●	Rejection of planning for reasons of nature protection	Exchange on planning decisions before the submission of the building application	Through owner, project manager, head of construction
Soil-conservation authority, Berlin Charlottenburg-Wilmersdorf	local authority; project approval	low	●	●			Through owner, project manager, head of construction
Senate Department for Economic Affairs, Energy and Public Enterprises	local authority; funding agency	medium	●	●	Budget overruns in funding program and resulting budget cuts; schedule/timeline issues	Cost monitoring, profitability analysis; planning variants; project management	Through owner, project manager, head of construction
Senate Department for Urban Development, Building and Housing	Local authority, examination of budget documents: architecture & technical systems	medium	●	●	Budget overruns and resulting budget cuts; schedule/timeline issues, content/ planning related issues	Cost monitoring, profitability analysis; variants, regular planning updates	Through owner, project manager, head of construction
Senate Department for Urban Mobility, Transport, Climate Action and the Environment	Local authority, examination of budget documents: Landscape	medium	●	●	Budget overruns and resulting budget cuts; schedule/timeline issues, content/ planning related issues	Cost monitoring, profitability analysis; variants, regular planning updates	Through owner, project manager, head of construction

GREENEST PROJECT STAKEHOLDER MAP

● LOW ● MEDIUM ● HIGH

DEMO SITE 1

Museum "Pavilion & Knowledge Paths"

Site Requirements:
Technologies – SPs to be implemented: SP1, SP 2, SP 3, SP 7, SP 14, SP 15, SP 16
Value chains-suppliers: TUB, ZRS, INEB, KMAEL, DAIK, THOLZ, HAMS, METSOL

Deadline: Friday, April 19, 2024

Stakeholders	Role in project	Level of Support	Interest	Impact/ Influence	Risks/ Uncertainties	Strategies	Interact Preferences
ZRS Architekten; Monique Bührdel	general planner architecture, project lead	high	●	●	Planning errors, delays in design process, change requests by clients, execution errors, unforeseen circumstances, public objections, and changes to laws etc.	Risk analysis & management, cost & schedule controlling, regular status updates to decision makers	through research coordinator (TUB)
Lavaland + Treibhaus; Deniz Diczli	Specialist planner, landscape architecture	high	●	●	as above	Risk analysis & management, cost & schedule controlling, regular status updates to decision makers	through research coordinator (TUB)
Tamschick Media + Space; Carsten Schildwächter	Specialist planner, exhibition design	high	●	●	Planning errors, delays in design process, change requests by clients, execution errors, unforeseen circumstances, public objections, and changes to laws etc.	Risk analysis & management, cost & schedule controlling, regular status updates to decision makers	through research coordinator (TUB)
ZRS Engineers; Uwe Seile	Specialist planner, structural engineering	high	●	●	as above	as above	Through general planner; research coordinator (TUB)
Ingenieurbüro Hausladen; Elisabeth Endres	Specialist planner, climate design	high	●	●	as above	as above	Through general planner; research coordinator (TUB)

GREENEST PROJECT STAKEHOLDER MAP

DEMO SITE 1

Museum "Pavilion & Knowledge Paths"

Site Requirements:
Technologies – SPs to be implemented: SP1, SP 2, SP 3, SP 7, SP 14, SP 15, SP 16
Value chains-suppliers: TUB, ZRS, INEB, KMAEL, DAIK, THOLZ, HAMS, METSOL

Deadline: Friday, April 19, 2024

Stakeholders	Role in project	Level of Support	Interest	Impact/ Influence	Risks/ Uncertainties	Strategies	Interact Preferences
Ingenieurbüro KEM; Mr. Schmaev	Specialist planner, technical systems	medium	●	●	as above	as above	Through general planner; research coordinator (TUB)
Ingenieurbüro Moll; Hr. Böhm	Specialist planner, acoustic	medium	●	●	as above	as above	Through general planner; research coordinator (TUB)
Schönherr landscape architecture; Hr. Schönherr	Specialist planner, landscape planning	high	●	●	as above	as above	Through general planner; research coordinator (TUB)
Fire Protection; Monique Bührdel	Specialist planner, fire protection	high	●	●	as above	as above	Through research coordinator (TUB)
Ecological Master plan; Eve Gehricke	Specialist planner, ecological master plan	high	●	●	as above	as above	Through general planner; research coordinator (TUB)

GREENEST PROJECT STAKEHOLDER MAP

DEMO SITE 1

Museum "Pavilion & Knowledge Paths"

Site Requirements:
Technologies – SPs to be implemented: SP1, SP 2, SP 3, SP 7, SP 14, SP 15, SP 16
Value chains-suppliers: TUB, ZRS, INEB, KMAEL, DAIK, THOLZ, HAMS, METSOL

Deadline: Friday, April 19, 2024

Stakeholders	Role in project	Level of Support	Interest	Impact/ Influence	Risks/ Uncertainties	Strategies	Interact Preferences
Inclusion & Accessibility; Lisa-Marie Kolbinger	Specialist planner, accessibility	high	●	●	as above	as above	Through research coordinator (TUB)
Terhalle Holzbau	Research partner/ manufacturer of WDLT-Slab	high	●	●	Implementation risk, material quality & quantity	Close collaboration and regular exchange	through project manager
BIMETICA	Research partner (SP 4, 5, 6)	high	●	●	Compatibility of data, lack of data	Close collaboration and regular exchange	through project manager
Netcompany Intrasoft	Research partner (SP 6)	high	●	●	Compatibility of data, lack of data	Close collaboration and regular exchange	through project manager
AMSolutions	Research partner (SP 16)	high	●	●	Implementation risk, compatibility with TU network and system	Risk analysis & management, close collaboration and regular exchange	Through project manager

5.4.2 DC#2 – Berlin Lodge

DC#2 has external and internal stakeholders. At present, there are not yet specific contact persons for all groups; they will be identified as the project progresses. The following groups of stakeholders were identified:

External:

1. Residents (Students)
2. Bezirksamt Berlin Lichtenberg - Bauaufsicht
3. Deutsches Institut für Bautechnik
4. General contractor
5. Insurer
6. Waste-wood-supplier
7. Wood-processing company

Internal:

1. HOWOGE
2. ZRS Architekten
3. Terhalle Holzbau
4. TU Berlin, Natural Building Lab
5. BIMETICA
6. Netcompany Intrasoft
7. AMSolutions

The following table is indicating the stakeholders map, describing the role of each stakeholder in the project, their level of influence and interest. Possible risks and uncertainties are indicated and the strategies that will be followed for their engagement.

GREENEST PROJECT STAKEHOLDER MAP

DEMO SITE 2

Berlin Lodge

Site Requirements:
Technologies – SPs to be implemented: SP4, SP5, SP6, SP7, SP11, SP16
Value chains-suppliers:

Deadline: Friday, April 19, 2024

Stakeholders	Role in project	Category / Level of Support	Interest	Impact/ Influence	Risks/ Uncertainties	Strategies	Interact Preferences
Residents (Students)	Users of monitored housing units	External	●	●	User behaviour may affect monitoring results, lack of acceptance may disrupt monitoring	Initial briefing, raising awareness and acceptance, informing about the role of user behaviour, swift response to technical issues	n/a
Bezirksamt Berlin Lichtenberg Bauaufsicht	Building authority	External	●	●	Process of granting building permit and technical approval may cause delays Authorisation for use is dependent on the approval of the test engineers	Early consultation, especially regarding technical approval of SP11	n/a
Deutsches Institut für Bautechnik	Institution granting technical approval	External	●	●	Technical approval may cause delays / long processing of application could rule out certain technical solutions	Early consultation regarding technical approval of SP11	n/a
General contractor (tbc.)	Architect and construction	External	●	●	Building parameters and detailed design have impact on design of SP11, project timeline is essential for research project / installation of SP11 / delay	Good preparation of the award procedure (market research), Close communication, early alignment regarding timelines, early	n/a
Insurer	Insure building	External	●	●	Construction not yet approved is not insured, no utilisation	Early consultation, use of authorized building materials	n/a

GREENEST PROJECT STAKEHOLDER MAP

DEMO SITE 2

Berlin Lodge

Site Requirements:

Technologies – SPs to be implemented: SP4, SP5, SP6, SP7, SP11, SP16

Value chains-suppliers:

Deadline: Friday, April 19, 2024

Stakeholders	Role in project	Category / Level of Support	Interest	Impact/ Influence	Risks/ Uncertainties	Strategies	Interact Preferences
Waste-Wood-Supplier (Owner/Source, tbc.)	Material supplier	External	●	●	Availability of "raw" material (quantity, quality, timing) has impact on design and realization of	Early Procurement, dealing with availabilities implementing SP7 / developing fallback options	n/a
Wood-processing company (tbc.)	Facilitator for waste-wood-processing	External	●	●	Availability of processed material (quantity, quality, timing) has impact on design and realization of	Early Procurement, dealing with availabilities implementing SP7 / developing fallback options	n/a

GREENEST PROJECT STAKEHOLDER MAP

DEMO SITE 2

Berlin Lodge

Site Requirements:

Technologies – SPs to be implemented: SP4, SP5, SP6, SP7, SP11, SP16

Value chains-suppliers:

Deadline: Friday, April 19, 2024

Stakeholders	Role in project	Category / Level of Support	Interest	Impact/ Influence	Risks/ Uncertainties	Strategies	Interact Preferences
HOWOGE	Research partner / building developer	Internal	●	●	Inefficiency (budget can potentially cause rescheduling)	Close collaboration and regular exchange	
ZRS Architekten	Research partner / developer of EcoTechWall (SP11)	Internal	●	●	not obtain the necessary authorisations	Close collaboration and regular exchange	
Terhalle Holzbau	Research partner / manufacturer of EcoTechWall (SP11)	Internal	●	●	Interface risk (material preservation, module production, window installation, module delivery for building integration)	Close collaboration and regular exchange	
TU Berlin, Natural Building Lab	Research partner / specializing in waste processing and design strategies (SP2, SP7)	Internal	●	●	Not enough suitable material	Close collaboration and regular exchange	
BIMETICA	Research partner / developer of GreenPlugin, ZeBIM and ASSESS-DST (SP4, SP5, SP6)	Internal	●	●		Close collaboration and regular exchange	

GREENEST PROJECT STAKEHOLDER MAP

● LOW
 ● MEDIUM
 ● HIGH

DEMO SITE 2

Berlin Lodge

Site Requirements:

Technologies – SPs to be implemented: SP4, SP5, SP6, SP7, SP11, SP16

Value chains-suppliers:

Deadline: Friday, April 19, 2024

Stakeholders	Role in project	Category / Level of Support	Interest	Impact/ Influence	Risks/ Uncertainties	Strategies	Interact Preferences
Netcompany Intrasoft	Research partner / developer of ASSESS-DST (SP6)	Internal	●	●		Close collaboration and regular exchange	
AMSolutions	Research partner / developer of NestControls (SP16)	Internal	●	●	System is not allowed to be installed or used because of unsolved risks (fire protection, data protection, maintenance)	Close collaboration and regular exchange	

5.4.3 DC#3 – Delta Info Centre

GREENEST PROJECT STAKEHOLDER MAP

DEMO SITE 3

PORTO VIRO
 Site Requirements: Location of demo site: PORTO LEVANTE (PORTO VIRO)
 Technologies – SPs to be implemented: DeltaSmart is a (prefabricated) modular building realized with multifunctional wall systems that combine active with passive technologies and designed for deconstruction and recycling. It will be located in the city of Porto Viro (Italy) and will accommodate a tourist office, as well as a recovery and maintenance depot for boats.

Deadline: Friday, April 19, 2024

Stakeholders	Role in project	Level of Support	Interest	Impact/Influence	Risks/ Uncertainties	Strategies	Interact Preferences
ENTE PARCO REGIONALE VENETO DELTA DEL PO	Politician	High	●	●		Continuous monitoring, regular support in building regulation	Email presidente@parcodeltapo.org
REGIONE DEL VENETO	Politician	High	●	●		Continuous monitoring, regular support in building regulation	Email Cristiano.corazzari@regione.veneto.it
2 emme service srl	Engineer	High	●	●		Continuous monitoring and support in technical choices	Email posta@2emmeservice.it
Tumiati Impiant srl	Engineer	Medium	●	●		Continuous monitoring and support in technical choices	Email info@tumiatiimpianti.it

Much of the information mentioned in these tables will be updated as the project progresses and will be reconsidered or confirmed and validated during the Stakeholders engagement plan.

5.4.4 DC#4 – North Aegean Recreational Centre

DC#4 is a site which at the moment has no use and therefore no specific users or residents can be identified. At the same time the site is located in a village in a remote area of Greece and therefore its market is quite localized. As a result, the stakeholders involved will be mostly people of Lesvos Island and the companies that will undertake the construction of the demo building, along with the technologies providers. A key stakeholder of DC#4 will be the Technical Department of the Municipality of Stypsi that should contribute in the establishment of the requirements of the demo site and will be involved in the related licensing. Taking the aforementioned data into account the following groups of stakeholders were identified:

1. MoS Technical Department
2. Suppliers (wood, sheep-wool, stone)
3. Constructors and construction companies
4. Neighbours, citizens
5. GreeNest Project technology providers

The following table indicates the stakeholders' map, describing the role of each stakeholder in the project, their level of influence and interest, the strategies that are suggested to follow for their engagement etc.

GREENEST PROJECT STAKEHOLDER MAP

DEMO SITE 4

“Youth Recreational Center in Stypsi, North Aegean”

Site Requirements:
 Technologies – SPs to be implemented: **SP4, SP5, SP6, SP8, SP9, SP13, SP14, SP15, SP16**
 Value chains-suppliers: **Local / Regional**

Deadline: Friday, April 19, 2024

Stakeholders	Role in project	Level of Support	Interest	Impact/ Influence	Risks/ Uncertainties	Strategies	Interact Preferences
Mantzaris D.	MoS Technical Department (Responsible)	High		Legislation audits may affect timelines and construction schedule	Continuous monitoring, regular updates, employee training, click response to emerging threats	N/A	
Drakoulas N.	MoS Technical Department (Responsible)	High		-//-	-//-	N/A	
Gianni Ath.	MoS Technical Department (Responsible)	High		-//-	-//-	N/A	
Chios N.	Woodworker – Supplier	(unclear at the moment)		Unclear instructions may delay production, availability of materials	Communicate and instruct on time, workshops, consult them regarding the materials	N/A	
Sakavas Th.	Woodworker – Supplier	(unclear at the moment)		-//-	-//-	N/A	

Stakeholders	Role in project	Level of Support	Interest	Impact/ Influence	Risks/ Uncertainties	Strategies	Interact Preferences
Pitsoulis N.	Construction	(unclear at the moment)	●	●	Unclear instructions may delay production	Communicate and instruct on time, seminars or workshops, project updates	N/A
Drakoulas N.	Construction	(unclear at the moment)	●	●	-/-	-/-	N/A
Komninos G.	Construction	(unclear at the moment)	●	●	-/-	-/-	N/A
Triantafyllou A.	Sheep wool Supplier	(unclear at the moment)	●	●	Amount of product supplied, depending on the season	Communicate and instruct on time, related seminars, frequent project updates	N/A
Tzamerikos A.	Sheep wool Supplier	(unclear at the moment)	●	●	-/-	-/-	N/A
Lithotomos N.	Sheep wool Supplier	(unclear at the moment)	●	●	-/-	-/-	N/A

Stakeholders	Role in project	Level of Support	Interest	Impact/ Influence	Risks/ Uncertainties	Strategies	Interact Preferences
Alexandris N.	Building Materials Supplier	(unclear at the moment)	●	●	Lack / Delay of materials may affect design and construction schedule	Communicate and inform frequently	N/A
Valasis S.	Neighbour	(unclear at the moment)	●	●	Possibility of annoyance during construction, may be unsatisfied with the result	Educate & raise awareness of project scope, explain project schedule, swift response to technical issues	N/A
Koutzpis D.	Neighbour	(unclear at the moment)	●	●	-/-	-/-	N/A
Manavis I.	Neighbour	(unclear at the moment)	●	●	-/-	-/-	N/A
Valioutis P.	Neighbour	(unclear at the moment)	●	●	-/-	-/-	N/A
Petrioti M.	Neighbour	(unclear at the moment)	●	●	-/-	-/-	N/A

Stakeholders	Role in project	Level of Support	Interest	Impact/ Influence	Risks/ Uncertainties	Strategies	Interact Preferences
BGTeC	Research partner / Technology provider	High	●	●	Delay of product supply may complicate design & production	Close collaboration and regular updates, brain-storming sessions, problem solving meetings	
HAMS	Research partner / Technology provider	High	●	●	-/-	-/-	
DAIK	Research partner / Technology provider	High	●	●	-/-	-/-	
METSOL	Research partner / Technology provider	High	●	●	-/-	-/-	

The tables presented in the previous pages initially identifying the basic stakeholders that were defined at the moment, for DC#4, based on the already known data and requirements. Their support for the project, their contact preferences and their involvement in the project were not yet determined at the phase that this table was created, as the project is still at a very early stage. Much of the information mentioned in these tables will be updated as the project progresses and will be reconsidered or confirmed and validated during the Stakeholders engagement plan.

6. Stakeholders Engagement Plan

Stakeholder engagement plan refers to a document or a plan which outlines how a project team identifies, analyzes, plans and implements actions to engage the stakeholders of a specific project. The needs of stakeholders are determined first and then the engagement plan will aid in figuring out how these needs will be met.

The engagement plan is usually created during the project's planning phase and can be adjusted or enriched as the project progresses.

Before the establishment of the different engagement activities, the stakeholders should be grouped according to their background, their needs, their relationship and impact on the project. There are different levels of stakeholders' engagement, however, the most common actions are informing, consulting, involving and collaborating with them. These actions are assigned to each stakeholder depending on their role in the project. For example, if the stakeholder is a key stakeholder, then he is actively involved, and if he is a neutral and secondary stakeholder then, he will be just informed.

In order to determine the appropriate level of engagement for each stakeholder, their interests and characteristics should be clarified as mentioned before but also, their related to the project knowledge, expertise, resources and position.

6.1 Strategies for Stakeholder engagement

Four are the basic levels of engagement and include informing, consulting, involving and collaborating. Each one of these engagement levels consists of different strategies and communication channels. A successful engagement plan should include all these engagement activities. Moreover, the following tips/instructions should be adopted:

- Creation of unique engagement strategies for each of the stakeholder groups.
- Lots of face-to-face communication should be promoted and foreseen with key stakeholders. Building trust with them first is critical for the success of the project.
- Communicating early and often is also important because people will need time to think before deciding.
- Each stakeholder should receive the right amount of information depending on their interest (others need just a summary and others may want to know every detail).
- If someone is opposed to the project, you can get the support first from someone with the same level of impact and then ask the latter to persuade the former.

The first level of engagement, “the informing action”, is usually performed for the stakeholders with low interest and low influence in the project. At this level, the aim is to just inform the stakeholders or give them frequent updates. Communication is mostly one-way in this case, and it is in their discretion to decide whether they will follow or read what is published.

Common ways of informing are:

- Social media pages
- Press release outlets
- Project website and blogs
- Digital newsletters and emails
- Public announcements

“Consulting stakeholders”, involves frequent communication with the interested stakeholders to seek their opinion, views, suggestions etc. These stakeholders may have a high interest in the project and moderate to low influence, however, their opinion could be heard and considered in the decision-making.

Strategies followed for consulting the stakeholders are:

- Discussion forums and online meetings
- Surveys and questionnaires
- Interviews
- In person meetings and public hearings

In this category of consulting, stakeholders of high influence and low interest could be also included therefore, they should be informed for more specific subjects and ask their feedback for these or should raise their awareness for specific issues in the project, by asking them to review documents or other material that could increase their interest. These stakeholders should be “kept satisfied” in order not to disturb the progress of the project.

“Involving stakeholders” refers to those who have high level of interest and moderate to high level of influence. This type of engaging requires involvement of the stakeholders in the decision-making and in the progress of the project, by participating in problem-solving, generating ideas, finding ways to overcome issues, etc. The stakeholders included in this category are seen as partners of the project and their feedback is valuable. They should receive a high level of information in different areas of the project and be always updated so that they could share their ideas and concerns.

The communication strategies usually adopted for involving this type of stakeholders are:

- Online meetings and focus groups
- Workshops

- Frequent updates via emails
- Have an open communication channel (phone calls) to inform them how their feedback has affected the project's progress and be able to keep them engaged.

Finally, the higher level of engagement is “collaborating” with the stakeholders and that means that this type of stakeholders participates in the project as partners. In this category, suppliers, constructors, designers etc. can be included and people or groups with a high level of interest and influence. In order to be able to participate, they should be also kept informed and involved.

Training courses and resources could be also provided for these stakeholders, to enhance their understanding and ability to contribute.

The communication channels that could be used in this case can include:

- Multi-stakeholder forums
- Facilitated workshops/seminars/courses
- Online platforms for sharing documents
- Joint planning sessions
- Frequent email correspondence

In general, all the stakeholders should be kept informed (at minimum), and as engaged as possible throughout the whole project's duration, and also:

- They should be treated with respect.
- The information provided to them must be carefully selected, and appropriate training, mentoring, or other support should be supplied to keep them involved.
- They should be involved when possible and as much as possible.
- Maintaining their enthusiasm by giving them feedback about their assistance/accomplishments and the final results of the project is also really important.
- Engaging them in decision-making could give them additional motivation.

6.2 Stakeholders' engagement plan (for each DC)

Below, will be presented the strategies and communication channels that will be used in each demonstration site, depending on the needs of their stakeholders. The strategies that are most commonly used to engage stakeholders in projects like GreeNest are:

1. Surveys and questionnaires: these can be addressed via online platforms or on paper at the demonstration sites.
2. Interviews with stakeholders to ask their opinion and feedback.

3. Online meetings to inform and involve them.
4. Joined platforms for sharing documents, data etc.
5. Workshops/events to train them and present them with the different technologies and how these will be installed and will be used.
6. Brochures and other informative material.

In addition, in order to engage all the interested parties from the beginning of the project, the following instructions can be adopted:

- a. Communicate the project and its needs as early as possible in order to give them time to think and decide whether they will participate or not.
- b. Schedule from the beginning of the project the necessary meetings and in person discussions with the defined key stakeholders.
- c. Attribute them roles and let them be as engaged as they want, to keep them satisfied.
- d. Train them and organise seminars so that they will obtain more expertise and be able to better contribute to the project.
- e. Give them motives or small “gifts” to engage the “difficult” and not interested parties.

6.2.1 DC#1 – Museum Pavilion & Knowledge Paths

Broad engagement of future users – TU community: students & professors

The planning for the new museum pavilion and redesign of the landscape has been developed by students of the TU Berlin since 2019 in various consecutive courses at Natural Building Lab (TU Berlin) in cooperation with other chairs and faculties at TU Berlin. Accompanied by an external advisory board, the student project office developed a final design approach that merged several years of conception and preliminary work. Within the framework of collaborative planning workshops, interim planning statuses were discussed in a transdisciplinary framework, planning variants and objectives were weighed up and the project was developed from within the university. Therefore, the stakeholders’ engagement activities have begun earlier for this demonstration site. In April 2022, the student design proposal was handed over to the expert planning team. The planning is currently adapted to the GreenNest solutions and SPs. The following actions are organized to communicate the project:

- Discussion forums and public planning workshops
- Project website, social media & press releases
- Meetings in focus groups with students and different stakeholders
- Communication formats: site model, exhibitions

- “Uni_verse”: Pop-Up Exhibition space at TU Berlin as a physical address for project related topics and progress updates (<https://www.tu.berlin/en/topics/knowledge-exchange/2021/dezember/a-new-space-for-science-communication>)
- Design Build Project “Re-construction site” as a communication infrastructure to activate the future site for new stakeholders and the TU community: <https://www.nbl.berlin/projects/experimentierfeld-baufeld/>

FIGURE 14: TEACHING AND LEARNING FORMATS IN DC#1

Collaborative & transdisciplinary Planning Workshops

The living lab "Museum Pavilion" is being designed in a participatory and transdisciplinary process bringing together knowledge and expertise from within and outside the university. A series of collaborative planning workshops were held at TU Berlin to promote interdisciplinary cooperation and the involvement of future users, representatives of public authorities and the building owner, as well as external experts. As part of these events, the planning status and key topics of the project were presented and discussed (semi-)publicly. Participants also included the authorities responsible for early involvement in the project and for early preparation of the approval of innovations. The presentation and discussion took place in various interactive workshop formats in large and small groups, and the results were compiled again in moderated formats. During the COVID pandemic, some of the workshops were held completely digitally, while others were hybrid in order to enable the lowest possible threshold for participation. The results of the events were recorded in minutes. A large moveable model was built for engaged planning in different locations and as a strong visual and interactive communication format. The workshops took place in different locations at TU Berlin to reach different groups and audiences.

- Public discussion forums with different stakeholders
- Planning workshops with advisory board, public authorities, users, building owner
- Facilitated workshops with focus groups
- Written summaries of workshop results as documentation method, contributed to involved actors via email
- Planning/discussion formats: model, maps, documents

FIGURE 15: INSIGHT INTO FOCUS-GROUP MEETINGS, THE PARTICIPATORY PLANNING WORKSHOPS & PUBLIC FORUMS

Engagement of future users – exhibitors

The future users were part of the project from the very beginning. The head of the mineralogical collection, the future exhibition team, as well as the project leader and owner have been part of the interdisciplinary project team at TU Berlin. They take part in planning workshops, regular organizational meetings and training workshops to project-related topics.

Before the student planning began, the rough requirements were summarized in writing by the different users and added with legal, financial and organizational requirements by the project management. They were the starting point for the design planning and were further specified during the planning process. After each planning workshop, the users' feedback was summarized and recorded. Activities that were organized:

- Facilitated training workshops and informative seminars on project-related topics
- Regular (online) meetings in focus groups
- Regular updates on project and planning development

The collaborative planning process of demo building DC#1 will be continued and further developed in order to ensure the further engagement of different stakeholders. Formats and methods for the implementation of the project in research, teaching and general activities at TU Berlin will be pursued:

- Public forums and events in planning & construction phases
- Project-related teaching formats to ensure student engagement
- Regular meetings in focus-groups
- Update and exchange between research and planning
- Publication of informative material & project updates, social media
- Written Project-updates to public authorities
- Project-related training workshops & seminars

To conclude, the following engagement plan was created for DC#1, as a result of all the aforementioned activities and will be updated and revised regularly during the whole project duration.

Stakeholder Engagement Plan

DEMO SITE Name			DEMO SITE Description						Project Manager/Responsible of DEMO				
Location of demo site & other info: e.g. Wall St. Pedestrian Walkway Campus of TU Berlin, Straße des 17. Juni 135, 10623 Berlin. Green area/former parking space behind the main building of TU Berlin, central Campus, limited access by car.			The building site is located on the south of the main TU building in the University Campus City West (UCCW) which covers an area approx. 13.101m2. The proposed building's architecture gives emphasis to the ecological / ZeB construction, as well as to the surrounding environment with emphasis to the existing trees located in the area which will be preserved. The new building will be used as a museum – exhibition center – knowledge hub where eco-friendly solutions for buildings to reach ZeB status will be demonstrated and exhibitions, conferences, seminars, knowledge days for professionals, students and visitors will be held.						GreenNest Project: Sina Jansen				
Basics			Project Information						Commitment Level				
									C - Current Level		R - Required Level		
Stakeholder	Title	Influence	Priority	SME?	Decision-Maker	Comm. Freq.	Information Type	Comm. Method	Against	Passive	Neutral	Helpful	Notes
Executive Board of Technical University Berlin	building owner	High	High	No	Yes	Monthly	Status update	Workshop			C	R	regular milestone: project presentation
Audrey Podann	Project Leader	High	High	No	Yes	Weekly	Strategic panning	Inperson				C	project meeting every two weeks
Sabine Kinzel	Head of construction; Project management	High	High	No	Yes	Weekly	Strategic panning	Inperson				C	project meeting every two weeks
René Vonau	Head of Buildings and Services Management, TU Berlin	Low	Low	No	No		Status update	Email		C	R		regular milestone: project presentation; individual exchange in between
District of Berlin Charlottenburg-Wilmersdorf	Local authority, funding recipient	Medium	Low	No	No	Monthly	Status update	Workshop				C	regular milestone: project presentation
Department "Science & Society", TU Berlin	End-User, Building Operator	Medium	Medium	No	Yes	Weekly	Progress to goal	Workshop				C	project meeting every two weeks
Mineralogical Collections (TUB)	End-User	Low	Medium	No	No	Monthly	Status update	Workshop				C	project meeting every four weeks
City planning office, Berlin Charlottenburg-Wilmersdorf	Local authority, project approval	Medium	Medium	No	Yes	Monthly	Status update	Email		C	R		regular milestone: project presentation
Historical Monuments Office, Berlin Charlottenburg-Wilmersdorf	Local authority, project approval	High	High	No	Yes	Monthly	Status update	Email		C	R		regular milestone: project presentation ; individual exchange in between
Garden Monuments Office, Berlin Charlottenburg-Wilmersdorf	Local authority, project approval	High	High	No	Yes	Monthly	Status update	Email		C	R		regular milestone: project presentation; individual exchange in between
Nature-conservation authority, Berlin Charlottenburg-Wilmersdorf	Local authority, project approval	Medium	Low	No	Yes	Monthly	Status update	Email			C		regular milestone: project presentation ; individual exchange in between
Soil-conservation authority, Berlin Charlottenburg-Wilmersdorf	Local authority, project approval	Medium	Low	No	No	Monthly	Status update	Email			C		regular milestone: project presentation ; individual exchange in between

Senate Department for Economic Affairs, Energy and Public Enterprises	Local authority, examination of budget documents	High	High	No	Yes	Monthly	Status update	Workshop			C	regular milestone: project presentation
Senate Department for Urban Development, Building and Housing	Local authority, examination of budget documents	High	High	No	Yes	Monthly	Status update	Workshop			C	regular milestone: project presentation
Senate Department for Urban Mobility, Transport, Climate Action and the Environment	Local authority, examination of budget documents	High	High	No	Yes	Monthly	Status update	Workshop			C	regular milestone: project presentation
ZRS Architects	Project Lead, Planning Team	High	High	Yes	No	Weekly	Strategic panning	Workshop			C	project meeting every two weeks
Lavaland +Treibhaus	Planning Team Landscape	Low	Low	Yes	No		Status update	Email			C	project meeting every two weeks
Tamschick Media + Space	Planning Team Exhibition	Low	Low	Yes	No		Status update	Email			C	project meeting every two weeks
ZRS Engineers	Plannig Team Structural Engineering	High	High	Yes	No	Weekly	Strategic panning	Workshop			C	project meeting every two weeks
Ingenieurbüro Hausladen	Planning Team, Climate Design	High	High	Yes	No	Weekly	Strategic panning	Workshop			C	project meeting every two weeks
Ingenieurbüro KEM	Planning Team Technical Systems	Medium	Low	Yes	No	Monthly	Strategic panning	Workshop			C	scheduling of individual meetings
Ingenieurbüro Moll	Planning Team Acoustic	Low	Low	Yes	No		Status update	Email			C	scheduling of individual meetings
Schönherr Landscape Architects	Plannig Team Landscape	Low	Low	Yes	No		Status update	Email			C	project meeting every two weeks
ZRS Architects Specialist planners	Planning Team Fire Protection ecological concept, accessibility	High	Medium	Yes	No		Status update	Email			C	scheduling of individual meetings
Citizens	Neighbors, visitors	Low	Low	No	No		Status update	Workshop			C	public milestone: project presentation
Students	Visitors, Users	Low	Low	No	No		Status update	Workshop			C	public milestone: project presentation
Research Institutions	Users, supporters	Low	Low	No	No		Status update	Workshop			C	public milestone: project presentation

6.2.2 DC#2 – Berlin Lodge

Stakeholder Engagement Plan														
DEMO SITE Name			DEMO SITE Description						Project Manager/Responsible of DEMO					
Location of demo site & other info: Alfred-Kowalke-Straße 22 10315 Berlin			DC#2 Berlin Lodge: The Demonstrator building is located in Berlin Lichtenberg, east of the city centre, directly adjacent to the big animal park "Tierpark". We want to build small apartments for students.											
Basics			Project Information						Commitment Level					
									C - Current Level			R - Required Level		
Stakeholder	Title	Influence	Priority	SME?	Decision-Maker	Comm. Freq.	Information Type	Comm. Method	Against	Passive	Neutral	Helpful	Notes	
Residents	Students	Low	Low	No	No	Monthly	Status update	Text		C		R	should accept the monitoring, certain user behaviour may be required	
Bezirksamt Berlin Lichtenberg	Local building authority	High	High	No	Yes	Monthly	Strategic planning	Email		C	R			
Deutsches Institut für Bautechnik	Authority for technical approval	High	Medium	No	Yes	Weekly	Progress to goal	Email			C	R		
tbc.	General Contractor	High	High	Yes	Yes	Weekly	Strategic planning	Online call			C	R	regular meetings	
tbc.	Insurer	Medium	Medium	No	No	Monthly	Progress to goal	Email		C	R			
tbc.	Waste-Wood-Supplier	Medium	Medium		No	Monthly	Progress to goal	Email			C	R		
tbc.	Wood-Processing Company	Medium	Medium	Yes	No	Monthly	Progress to goal	Email			C	R		

6.2.1 DC#3 – Delta Info Centre

Stakeholder Engagement Plan														
DEMO SITE Name			DEMO SITE Description						Project Manager/Responsible of DEMO					
Location of demo site & other info: PORTO LEVANTE (PORTO VIRO)			DeltaSmart is a (prefabricated) modular building realized with multifunctional wall systems that combine active with passive technologies and designed for deconstruction and recycling. It will be located in the city of Porto Viro (Italy) and will accommodate a tourist office, as well as a recovery and maintenance depot for boats.						Arch. Davide Marangoni					
Basics			Project Information						Commitment Level					
									C - Current Level			R - Required Level		
Stakeholder	Title	Email	Influence	Priority	SME?	Decision-Maker	Comm. Freq.	Information Type	Comm. Method	Against	Passive	Neutral	Helpful	Notes
ENTE PARCO REGIONALE VENETO DELTA DEL PO	Politician	direzione@r	High	High	No	No	Weekly	Status update	In Person			C	R	
REGIONE VENETO	Politician	cristiano.cor	High	Medium	No	No	Monthly	Status update	Email			C	R	
2 EMME SERVICE SRL	Engineer	posta@2em	Medium	Medium	Yes	No	Monthly	Brainstorming session	Phone		C		R	
TUMIATI IMPIANTI	Engineer	info@tumiat	Medium	Medium	Yes	No	Monthly	Brainstorming session	Phone		C		R	
DELTA GROUP	Engineer	info@deltag	Medium	Medium	Yes	No	Monthly	Brainstorming session	Phone		C		R	
AGRI FREE	Engineer	info@agrifree	Low	Low	Yes	No	Monthly	Status update	Phone		C		R	
FINPESCA	Owner	alessandro@	Medium	Medium	No	No	Monthly	Brainstorming session	Email		C		R	

6.2.2 DC#4 – North Aegean Recreational Centre

For the Greek demo-site, in person sessions with the local administrators of the demonstration site and the different local suppliers, have already took place in February – March 2024 and had as a target to inform them about the GREENEST project and to collect some preliminary information about their expectations and requirements for the demonstration building. During these sessions, the need to construct a youth recreational center was expressed, which could be used to organize seminars, exercise events, workshops etc. In addition, the different stakeholders that could assist in the project or participate in the project (suppliers, constructors etc.) were defined and informed in order to be engaged.

The target group of the Greek demo site after the completion of the construction works, are especially personnel, young people, tourists, students and families.

The main social innovation activities to be carried out (in Task 1.5) are related to the acceptance of the ecosystems/technologies that will be installed at the demo site and the involvement of the end-users/visitors to the energy efficiency concept. Their familiarization with the concept of building structures with local and earthen materials will be also intended.

TABLE 3: GENERIC SOCIAL ACTIVITIES PLAN FOR THE GREEK DEMO CASE

Generic Greek Demo-Site Plan for End-Users	
Target Group	Workers, personnel, visitors, tourists etc.
Social Activities to be carried out (during construction process and afterwards)	Workshops, brochures, living-lab, events focused on the promotion of green technologies and earthen materials.
Beneficiaries of social activities	Citizen groups and professionals interested in energy efficiency and sustainability, green techs, innovation etc.
Time plan for scheduled social activities	After six months from now, so that there will be some more progress in the project.
Way of communicating the social activities	Through advertising the events in the website of the Municipality, or the local newspapers etc.
Evaluation of social activities	Through questionnaires and interviews.

In continuation to the meetings held with the administrators and the local suppliers and constructors in the area of the demo site, an engagement plan was also created to define the ways that should be used to inform, contact and involve all the interested parties. This plan was developed in an excel form and will be updated and reexamined as the project progresses.

Stakeholder Engagement Plan													
DEMO SITE Name			DEMO SITE Description						Project Manager/Responsible of DEMO				
Location of demo site & other info: e.g. Wall St. Pedestrian Walkway			DEMO SITE #4: North Aegean Recreational Center. Location: Stypsi, Lesvos, GREECE Owner: Municipality of Stypsi						Dimitrios Mantzaris, Municipality of Stypsi				
Basics			Project Information						Commitment Level				
Stakeholder	Title	Influence	Priority	SME?	Decision-Maker	Comm. Freq.	Information Type	Comm. Method	Against	Passive	Neutral	Helpful	Notes
									C - Current Level		R - Required Level		
Mantzaris D.	Engineer-technical department	High	High	No	Yes	Monthly	Progress to goal	In Person				C	Also Email updates
Drakoulas N.	Engineer-technical department	High	High	No	Yes	Monthly	Progress to goal	Email			C	R	Also InPerson meetings
Yanni A.	Engineer-technical department	High	High	No	Yes	Monthly	Progress to goal	Email				R	Also InPerson meetings
Chios N.	Wood worker-supplier	Low	Medium	No	No	Monthly	Status update	Phone			C	R	
Sakavas Th.	Wood worker-supplier	Low	Medium	No	No	Monthly	Status update	Phone			C	R	
Pitsoulis N.	Construction company	Medium	Medium	Yes	No	Monthly	Status update	Inperson		C		R	
Drakoulas N.	Construction company	Medium	Medium	No	No	Monthly	Status update	Inperson			C	R	
Kominos I.	Constructor	Medium	Medium	No	No	Monthly	Status update	Inperson			C		
Triantafyllou A.	Sheepwool supplier	Low	High	No	No	Monthly	Strategic planning	Phone				C	Also update of the status of project will be provided
Tzamerikos A.	Sheepwool supplier	Low	High	No	No	Monthly	Strategic planning	Phone				C	
Lithotomos N.	Sheepwool supplier	Low	High	No	No	Monthly	Strategic planning	Phone				R	
Alexandris N.	Building Materials Supplier	Medium	High	No	No	Monthly	Status update	Inperson			C	R	
Valassis S.	Neighbours of the site area	Medium	Medium	No	No	Monthly	Status update	Inperson					In general, the neighbours should be informed, and be kept satisfied so as to have them on board. We need to make them supportive to the project and to avoid bringing us any obstacles.
Koutzpis D.													
Manavis I.													
Valioutis P.													
Petrioti M.													
BGTec	Greenest Technology provider	High	High	Yes	Yes	Weekly	Brainstorming session	Email				C	
HAMS	Greenest Technology provider	High	High	Yes	Yes	Weekly	Strategic planning	Email				C	
DAIKIN	Greenest Technology provider	High	High	No	Yes	Monthly	Strategic planning	Email				C	
METSOL	Greenest Technology provider	High	High	Yes	Yes	Monthly	Strategic planning	Email				C	
End-users	Workers, visitors	Low	Medium	No	No	Monthly	Progress to goal	Workshop			C	R	This group of end-users will be contacted and engaged in the next stages of the project. The basic communication method will be brochures and workshops/events to inform them.

7. Specified innovative social activities for involving additional stakeholders

As was already mentioned in the framework of other tasks of the Greenest Project (e.g. Task 1.5, Task 1.6, etc.) other social activities and communication methods will be organized, in order to communicate the project, inform and involve a broader range of stakeholders. In this aspect, not only people and groups related to the project or in the areas of the demo sites will be involved but also, other groups of stakeholders in other areas and from different backgrounds.

This will be achieved by creating, organizing, hosting and executing workshops, Living labs and /or hands-on actions or specialized events in fields closely related to the project and to the technologies/materials that will be applied.

7.1 Living Lab Museums – Pavilion – Collaboration of research & practice

Alternative planning processes & new actor constellations (integrative approach of research and practice to anchor transdisciplinary, participatory and experimental formats in planning and construction projects)

Increasingly complex requirements for planning and construction in the building sector lead in practice to diverse constellations of stakeholders, experts to be involved, as well as processes and interdependencies. The necessary innovations in sustainable circular construction are often more difficult to implement and specific gained knowledge remains in individual projects. As part of the living lab “Museum-Pavilion” of TU Berlin, experimental approaches on the production of new knowledge in and for the building sector are followed in close cooperation with stakeholders from building practice, future users and approval authorities. Formats such as participatory and transdisciplinary planning workshops and integrated teaching and learning formats, as well as regular exchange between involved stakeholders in forums, focus groups, meetings and seminars create an alternative process-approach to circular, innovative building design.

The pavilion is a lighthouse project for circular planning and construction and will be built entirely from reused or renewable raw materials. The aim of the planning is to develop and implement innovative, constructive solutions for building with reused and recycled building materials. In order to do so, the living lab cooperates with various research projects and institutions from TU Berlin and beyond. As the GreenNest project illustrates, through integrated processes of research and practice, a holistic planning and consideration approach, the definition of new value chains and the use of alternative planning tools, it is possible to react flexibly to existing material pools and plan in a future-oriented and circular manner:

- Workshops on interface topics with research and planning teams
- Online platforms for file and knowledge exchange
- Regular (online) meetings with update on planning and research process

- Collaborative risk analysis and management for the implementation of solutions in construction project
- Updates via email

FIGURE 16: ASSOCIATED RESEARCH PROJECTS & COLLABORATIONS ON REUSE MATERIALS, CIRCULAR DESIGN & LOWTECH

7.2 Stakeholders' groups involved in laboratory investigation and design of the light clay module

One of the aims of the GreeNest project is the investigation of the application of earth as a building material in a new light clay building module. The light clay module is a new non load bearing building material constructed from a timber frame, raw earth and waste additives. Piliko and NTUA Laboratory of Building materials aim to make a high-quality and sustainable material to cover the market and legislative gap for the southern European and Mediterranean areas. The Light clay module will be investigated to be flexible and easy applicable in several loadbearing structures, mostly from timber, and will be a possible alternative building material in the DCs.

A series of laboratory tests on earth and additives samples will be performed in the framework of the light clay living lab, in order to be used for the production of the light clay module. This module will have a vast application in new construction systems with natural materials.

The involved stakeholders for the laboratory investigation are mostly academics and students. During the design of the light clay module, stakeholders will have the chance to participate in hands-on workshops and understand the philosophy of the earthen buildings. At the end of the light clay module research, architects, civil and mechanical engineers, construction companies and owners will be the stakeholders' groups that will be able to use this new material.

8. Conclusions

The aim of this report was to define the site and stakeholders' requirements in terms of the GreeNest project in the four demonstration cases. The unique characteristics of each demonstration area paired together with the owners' and other stakeholders' requirements, contributed to the specification of the technologies that will be used in each site and gave important input for the preliminary design of these technologies (SPs) that will take place in WP3 of the project.

Additionally, the recognition of "helpful or negative" stakeholders, gives the project team the opportunity to organize the necessary actions to raise their interest and awareness and keep them involved in a way that will not jeopardize the project. It is important to know from the beginning of a project who are the supporters and who need to be convinced of the advantages of the project. With the stakeholders' engagement plan that was drafted for each demo site, the key stakeholders were defined, and the basic communication strategies were established. This plan will be updated as the project progresses with new findings and new communication methods. Some stakeholders may be removed as they may be no longer relevant, while new stakeholders could be added as they are involved in later stages of the project.

The engagement plan will be reviewed in the frame of T1.6: Stakeholders engagement–LivingLab Assessment (M7-M46). The strategies and actions that were defined in D1.4 will be carried out in T1.6 and will give feedback to the other tasks of the project. After the construction of the GreeNest demonstration buildings and their handing over to the owners, the feedback of the final end users will be reached via in person interviews and online or printed questionnaires.

9. References

<https://asana.com/resources/stakeholder-engagement-plan-template>

<https://simplystakeholders.com/>

<https://www.tractivity.co.uk/blog/levels-of-stakeholder-engagement>

<https://www.projectmanager.com/blog/stakeholder-mapping-guide>

<https://miro.com/blog/stakeholder-mapping/>

<https://templatelab.com/stakeholder-map/>

10. Annex

<h3 style="text-align: center;">Stakeholder Engagement Plan DC#1</h3>													
DEMO SITE Name			DEMO SITE Description					Project Manager/Responsible of DEMO					
Location of demo site & other info: e.g. Wall St. Pedestrian Walkway Campus of TU Berlin, Straße des 17. Juni 135, 10623 Berlin. Green area/former parking space behind the main building of TU Berlin, central Campus, limited access by car.			The building site is located on the south of the main TU building in the University Campus City West (UCCW) which covers an area approx. 13.101m ² . The proposed building's architecture gives emphasis to the ecological / ZeB construction, as well as to the surrounding environment with emphasis to the existing trees located in the area which will be preserved. The new building will be used as a museum – exhibition center – knowledge hub where eco-friendly solutions for buildings to reach ZeB status will be demonstrated and exhibitions, conferences, seminars, knowledge days for professionals, students and visitors will be held.					GreeNest Project: Sina Jansen					
Basics			Project Information					Commitment Level					
								C - Current Level		R - Required Level			
Stakeholder	Title	Influence	Priority	SME	Decision-Maker	Comm. Freq.	Information Type	Comm. Method	Against	Passive	Neutral	Helpful	Notes
Executive Board of Technical University Berlin	building owner	High	High	No	Yes	Monthly	Status update	Workshop			C	R	regular milestone: project presentation
Audrey Podann	Project Leader	High	High	No	Yes	Weekly	Strategic panning	Inperson				C	project meeting every two weeks
Sabine Kinzel	Head of construction; Project management	High	High	No	Yes	Weekly	Strategic panning	Inperson				C	project meeting every two weeks
René Vonau	Head of Buildings and Services Management, TU Berlin	Low	Low	No	No		Status update	Email		C		R	regular milestone: project presentation; individual exchange in between

District of Berlin Charlottenburg- Wilmersdorf	Local authority, funding recipient	Medium	Low	No	No	Monthly	Status update	Workshop			C		regular milestone: project presentation
Department "Science & Society", TU Berlin	End-User, Building Operator	Medium	Medium	No	Yes	Weekly	Progress to goal	Workshop				C	project meeting every two weeks
Mineralogical Collections (TUB)	End-User	Low	Medium	No	No	Monthly	Status update	Workshop				C	project meeting every four weeks
City planning office, Berlin Charlottenburg- Wilmersdorf	Local authority, project approval	Medium	Medium	No	Yes	Monthly	Status update	Email		C	R		regular milestone: project presentation
Historical Monuments Office, Berlin Charlottenburg- Wilmersdorf	Local authority, project approval	High	High	No	Yes	Monthly	Status update	Email		C	R		regular milestone: project presentation ; individual exchange in between
Garden Monuments Office, Berlin Charlottenburg- Wilmersdorf	Local authority, project approval	High	High	No	Yes	Monthly	Status update	Email		C	R		regular milestone: project presentation; individual exchange in between
Nature-conservation authority, Berlin Charlottenburg- Wilmersdorf	Local authority, project approval	Medium	Low	No	Yes	Monthly	Status update	Email				C	regular milestone: project presentation ; individual exchange in between
Soil-conservation authority, Berlin Charlottenburg- Wilmersdorf	Local authority, project approval	Medium	Low	No	No	Monthly	Status update	Email				C	regular milestone: project presentation ; individual exchange in between
Senate Department for Economic Affairs, Energy and Public Enterprises	Local authority, examination of budget documents	High	High	No	Yes	Monthly	Status update	Workshop				C	regular milestone: project presentation
Senate Department for Urban	Local authority,	High	High	No	Yes	Monthly	Status update	Workshop				C	regular milestone: project presentation

Development, Building and Housing	examination of budget documents												
Senate Department for Urban Mobility, Transport, Climate Action and the Environment	Local authority, examination of budget documents	High	High	No	Yes	Monthly	Status update	Workshop			C		regular milestone: project presentation
ZRS Architects	Project Lead, Planning Team	High	High	Yes	No	Weekly	Strategic panning	Workshop			C		project meeting every two weeks
Lavaland +Treibhaus	Planning Team Landscape	Low	Low	Yes	No		Status update	Email			C		project meeting every two weeks
Tamschick Media + Space	Planning Team Exhibition	Low	Low	Yes	No		Status update	Email			C		project meeting every two weeks
ZRS Enginerrrs	Plannig Team Structural Engineering	High	High	Yes	No	Weekly	Strategic panning	Workshop			C		project meeting every two weeks
Ingenieurbüro Hausladen	Planning Team, Climate Design	High	High	Yes	No	Weekly	Strategic panning	Workshop			C		project meeting every two weeks
Ingenieurbüro KEM	Planning Team Technical Systems	Medium	Low	Yes	No	Monthly	Strategic panning	Workshop			C		scheduling of individual meetings
Ingenieurbüro Moll	Planning Team Acoustic	Low	Low	Yes	No		Status update	Email			C		scheduling of individual meetings
Schönherr Landscape Architects	Plannig Team Landscape	Low	Low	Yes	No		Status update	Email			C		project meeting every two weeks
ZRS Architects Specialist planners	Planning Team Fire Protection	High	Medium	Yes	No		Status update	Email			C		scheduling of individual meetings

	ecological concept, accessibility												
Citizens	Neighbors, visitors	Low	Low	No	No		Status update	Workshop			C		public milestone: project presentation
Students	Visitors, Users	Low	Low	No	No		Status update	Workshop			C		public milestone: project presentation
Research Institutions	Users, supporters	Low	Low	No	No		Status update	Workshop			C		public milestone: project presentation

Stakeholder Engagement Plan DC#2

DEMO SITE Name			DEMO SITE Description						Project Manager/Responsible of DEMO				
Location of demo site & other info: Alfred-Kowalke-Straße 22 10315 Berlin			DC#2 Berlin Lodge: The Demonstrator building is located in Berlin Lichtenberg, east of the city centre, directly adjacent to the big animal park "Tierpark". We want to build small apartments for students.										
Basics			Project Information						Commitment Level				
									C - Current Level		R - Required Level		
Stakeholder	Title	Influence	Priority	SME?	Decision-Maker	Comm. Freq.	Information Type	Comm. Method	Against	Passive	Neutral	Helpful	Notes
Residents	Students	Low	Low	No	No	Monthly	Status update	Text		C		R	should accept the monitoring, certain user behaviour may be required
Bezirksamt Berlin Lichtenberg	Local building authority	High	High	No	Yes	Monthly	Strategic panning	Email		C	R		
Deutsches Institut für Bautechnik	Authority for technical approval	High	Medium	No	Yes	Weekly	Progress to goal	Email			C	R	
tbc.	General Contractor	High	High	Yes	Yes	Weekly	Strategic panning	Online call			C	R	regular meetings
tbc.	Insurer	Medium	Medium	No	No	Monthly	Progress to goal	Email		C	R		
tbc.	Waste-Wood-Supplier	Medium	Medium		No	Monthly	Progress to goal	Email			C	R	
tbc.	Wood-Processing Company	Medium	Medium	Yes	No	Monthly	Progress to goal	Email			C	R	

Stakeholder Engagement Plan DC#3

DEMO SITE Name				DEMO SITE Description						Project Manager/Responsible of DEMO				
Location of demo site & other info: PORTO LEVANTE (PORTO VIRO)				DeltaSmart is a (prefabricated) modular building realized with multifunctional wall systems that combine active with passive technologies and designed for deconstruction and recycling. It will be located in the city of Porto Viro (Italy) and will accommodate a tourist office, as well as a recovery and maintenance depot for boats.						Arch. Davide Marangoni				
Basics				Project Information						Commitment Level				
										C - Current Level		R - Required Level		
Stakeholder	Title	Email	Influence	Priority	SME?	Decision-Maker	Comm. Freq.	Information Type	Comm. Method	Against	Passive	Neutral	Helpful	Notes
ENTE PARCO REGIONALE VENETO DELTA DEL PO	Politician	direzione@parcodeltapo.org	High	High	No	No	Weekly	Status update	In Person			C	R	
REGIONE VENETO	Politician	cristiano.corazzari@regione.veneto.it	High	Medium	No	No	Monthly	Status update	Email			C	R	
2 EMME SERVICE SRL	Engineer	posta@2emmeservice.it	Medium	Medium	Yes	No	Monthly	Brainstorming session	Phone		C		R	
TUMIATI IMPIANTI	Engineer	info@tumiatiimpianti.it	Medium	Medium	Yes	No	Monthly	Brainstorming session	Phone		C		R	
DELTA GROUP	Engineer	info@deltagroupagroalimentare.com	Medium	Medium	Yes	No	Monthly	Brainstorming session	Phone		C		R	
AGRI FREE	Engineer	info@agrifree.shop	Low	Low	Yes	No	Monthly	Status update	Phone		C		R	
FINPESCA	Owner	alessandro@finpesca.it	Medium	Medium	No	No	Monthly	Brainstorming session	Email		C		R	

Stakeholder Engagement Plan DC#4

DEMO SITE Name			DEMO SITE Description						Project Manager/Responsible of DEMO				
Location of demo site & other info: e.g. Wall St. Pedestrian Walkway			DEMO SITE #4: North Aegean Recreational Center. Location: Stypsi, Lesvos, GREECE Owner: Municipality of Stypsi						Dimitrios Mantzaris, Municipality of Stypsi				
Basics			Project Information						Commitment Level				
									C - Current Level		R - Required Level		
Stakeholder	Title	Influence	Priority	SME?	Decision-Maker	Comm. Freq.	Information Type	Comm. Method	Against	Passive	Neutral	Helpful	Notes
Mantzaris D.	Engineer-technical department	High	High	No	Yes	Monthly	Progress to goal	In Person				C	Also Email updates
Drakoulas N.	Engineer-technical department	High	High	No	Yes	Monthly	Progress to goal	Email			C	R	Also InPerson meetings
Yanni A.	Engineer-technical department	High	High	No	Yes	Monthly	Progress to goal	Email				R	Also InPerson meetings
Chios N.	Wood worker-supplier	Low	Medium	No	No	Monthly	Status update	Phone			C	R	
Sakavas Th.	Wood worker-supplier	Low	Medium	No	No	Monthly	Status update	Phone			C	R	
Pitsoulis N.	Construction company	Medium	Medium	Yes	No	Monthly	Status update	Inperson		C		R	
Drakoulas N.	Construction company	Medium	Medium	No	No	Monthly	Status update	Inperson			C	R	
Komninos I.	Constructor	Medium	Medium	No	No	Monthly	Status update	Inperson			C		
Triantafyllou A.	Sheepwool supplier	Low	High	No	No	Monthly	Strategic planning	Phone				C	Also update of the status of project will be provided
Tzanerikos A.	Sheepwool supplier	Low	High	No	No	Monthly	Strategic planning	Phone				C	
Lithotomos N.	Sheepwool supplier	Low	High	No	No	Monthly	Strategic planning	Phone				R	

Alexandris N.	Building Materials Supplier	Medium	High	No	No	Monthly	Status update	Inperson				C	R	
Valassis S.	Neighbours of the site area	Medium	Medium	No	No	Monthly	Status update	Inperson						In general, the neighbours should be informed, and be kept satisfied so as to have them on board. We need to make them supportive to the project and to avoid bringing us any obstacles.
Koutzpis D.														
Manavis I.														
Valioutis P.														
Petrioti M.														
BGTec	Greenest Technology provider	High	High	Yes	Yes	Weekly	Brainstorming session	Email					C	
HAMS	Greenest Technology provider	High	High	Yes	Yes	Weekly	Strategic planning	Email					C	
DAIKIN	Greenest Technology provider	High	High	No	Yes	Monthly	Strategic planning	Email					C	
METSOL	Greenest Technology provider	High	High	Yes	Yes	Monthly	Strategic planning	Email					C	
End-users	Workers, visitors	Low	Medium	No	No	Monthly	Progress to goal	Workshop				C	R	This group of end-users will be contacted and engaged in the next stages of the project. The basic communication method will be brochures and workshops/events to inform them.

